

Demo: An Open-Source and Standards-Based Network-as-a-Service Platform for Cloud VR Gaming

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Abstract—This paper presents a novel end-to-end quality-on-demand Optical Network-as-a-Service (NaaS) platform that introduces cutting-edge Fifth Generation Fixed Network Advanced (F5G-A) access and transport network capabilities to enterprises, users, and application developers. We demonstrate this platform through a real cloud-based virtual reality (VR) gaming service use-case. The platform is supported by a number of open-source projects (i.e., ETSI OpenSource MANO, ETSI TeraFlowSDN), and its implementation is standards-based (GSMA Open Gateway, Linux Foundation CAMARA, ETSI ISG ZSM and F5G). The platform’s architecture, and its implementation are discussed. The paper also demonstrates a real end-to-end connectivity service via a F5G-A network slice realized by an end-to-end, Layer 3 VPN (L3VPN) service in order to show and validate the proof-of-concept (PoC).

Keywords— CAMARA, ETSI TeraFlowSDN, ETSI F5G, ETSI ZSM, Cloud AR/VR Gaming, Network Automation, Open-Source.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud-based augmented reality/virtual reality (AR/VR) gaming refers to a form of gaming, where the processing power and rendering capabilities required for AR/VR experiences are offloaded to cloud servers instead of being handled locally on the user’s device. In this model, the AR/VR content is streamed to the user’s device over the network and the device acts as a display and input interface, transmitting user commands back to the cloud server. Cloud AR/VR gaming offers several advantages and overcomes certain limitations of traditional AR/VR gaming setups: 1) Device independence and Lower Hardware Costs: With cloud AR/VR gaming, the user’s device requirements are reduced as the heavy computational tasks are performed on the cloud server. This means that even devices with limited processing power and lower costs can access and

enjoy high-quality AR/VR experiences. Users can potentially access AR/VR games on a wide range of devices including smartphones, tablets, low-spec PCs, or dedicated lightweight VR headsets. 2) Scalability: Cloud-based infrastructures allows for greater scalability in terms of user capacity. 3) Reduced Latency and Jitter: By leveraging cloud servers located in closer proximity to users, as well as using optical-based networks, cloud AR/VR gaming can potentially minimize latency and jitter, delivering smoother and more responsive experiences. Lower latency is crucial in AR/VR gaming to maintain a sense of immersion and to ensure that interactions feel immediate and natural.

GSMA Cloud AR/VR whitepaper [1] provides an overview of Cloud AR/VR Gaming applications. In order to offer a guaranteed Quality of Experience (QoE) for such demanding applications, the capabilities of the underlying Fixed-5G Advanced (F5G-A) [2] networks should be used. The F5G-A architecture exploits the optical network capacities to provide high quality transmission with ultra-low end-to-end (E2E) latency, guaranteed high bandwidth, and minimized jitter to ensure the QoE for cloud-based services.

The GSMA’s Open Gateway initiative [3] exposes the capabilities of the telco networks through a set of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). These APIs represent a paradigm shift in the way the global telecom industry designs and brings to market new immersive services. These APIs are defined, developed, and published in CAMARA [4], the open-source project for developers to access enhanced network capabilities. The availability of standardized, open, and reusable network APIs will be essential for enabling innovative services and use-cases. Our Network as a Service (NaaS) platform presented in this paper implements several CAMARA APIs and allows application developers to better offer their services to

their users, ensuring QoE and service isolation through the usage of a 5G network slice and an end-to-end L3VPN service. We demonstrate this innovative NaaS solution by a real cloud-based AR/VR game service. To the best of our knowledge, the framework presented in this paper is the first of its kind open-source, model-driven and standards-based development effort in NaaS platforms. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. The open-source projects relevant to the framework’s implementation are discussed in Section II. Section III is devoted to the standards-based architecture of our platform and its implementation, as well as our testbed and lab equipment used in this demo. We also illustrated a gaming use-case which is realized through the presented framework. This use case demonstration shows how our NaaS platform can be used as a means of network automation supporting such high experience services. The demo setup is explained in section IV. Our conclusions and the future work are discussed in section V.

II. OPEN-SOURCE PROJECTS INTEGRATED IN THIS FRAMEWORK

This section highlights the open-source projects we integrated in our NaaS platform implementation.

A. CAMARA

The capabilities of telco networks, while partly existing in 4G, have been significantly enhanced in the 5G network, offering greater power and versatility. These capabilities not only facilitate the extraction of information from the network, but also allow for network configuration. The exposure of these capabilities on demand, through a set of APIs, lays the groundwork for the evolution of operator networks into service enablement platforms. CAMARA, operating as an open-source initiative under the Linux Foundation, is dedicated to the definition, development, and testing of those APIs. The transition from network APIs to service APIs is imperative for simplifying telco complexity, thereby making APIs accessible to customers without telco expertise. In the proposed NaaS platform, we implement two categories of APIs in CAMARA: Quality-on-Demand (QoD) and Edge-Cloud: The QoD API provides a programmable interface for developers and other users (capabilities consumers) to implement traffic management policies on top of Operator’s internet connectivity services. More specifically, using QoD APIs, users can request on demand specific traffic profiles to be configured at end-user’s residential Home WiFi Access Point in order to ensure the required QoE for those services/applications running on a specific home device. QoD APIs could be useful in scenarios where a user is using head-mounted display device for VR/AR applications. VR/AR applications require high bandwidth for the big amount of data to be streamed [5]. The Edge-Cloud API provides the customer the ability to: 1) Provide and manage application images to be deployed on resources within the operator network; 2) Use reserved compute resources within the operator network for the deployment of applications on Virtual Machines (VMs) or containers; and 3) Influence the traffic routing from the user device towards the Edge instance of the Application [6].

B. ETSI ZSM, F5G, TeraFlowSDN, and Open-Source MANO

In this project we collaborate with the European Telecommunication Standard Institute (ETSI) Zero-touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) [7] and Fifth Generation Fixed Network (F5G) [2] community, not only to improve our design by exploiting the solutions from the ZSM and F5G standards, but also to help validate the ZSM and F5G standards by conducting and examining the proof-of-concept (PoC) demonstrations of our NaaS platform. The building blocks of the ZSM Framework are Management Domains (MDs). An MD has clearly defined interfaces that can be consumed by other MDs. A special MD in the ZSM Framework is called the E2E Service MD. It is responsible for the end-to-end service orchestration and directly interacts with the user. Other MDs do not interact directly with the user.

The ETSI TeraFlowSDN (TFS) [8] is a cloud-native SDN controller that aims to provide intelligent connectivity services for next-generation networks extending beyond the capabilities of 5G. We have integrated TeraFlowSDN in our NaaS platform as our F5G-A Network Management Domain (MD) (we developed code and contributed our implementation to TFS open-source community). We also integrated ETSI Open-Source Management and Orchestration (MANO) (OSM) [9] in our NaaS platform as our E2E Management Domain. OSM delivers a production-quality MANO stack that meets operators’ requirements for commercial NFV deployments.

III. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

This section provides an overview of the architecture of our platform and the testbed on which we tested this PoC.

A. Platform’s Architecture

The architecture of our platform, shown in Fig. 1, operates on a hierarchical model using standardized data models and interfaces.

Fig. 1: Our NaaS Platform’s Architecture

At its core, the Cloud VR Game Developer (top) issues a request to the CAMARA application manager in order to deploy the Gaming Application and its connectivity requirements. After that, ETSI OSM is used to configure the cloud computing resources through OpenStack APIs, and to orchestrate the connectivity services between the User VR Equipment and the Cloud Gaming Servers through the F5G-A network controlled and managed by ETSI TeraFlowSDN controller. The overall workflow used to deploy the Gaming Service starts when the game developer requests the installation of its Gaming Server in the cloud infrastructure. This interaction is triggered through the CAMARA Edge Cloud API that in turn, sends the appropriate requests to our OpenStack cloud resource manager through OSM, resulting in the creation of the VM that hosts the game server application. Once the Gaming Server is ready, the Game Client/User can send requests to play the cloud-based VR game by calling CAMARA's Quality-on-Demand (QoD) APIs to orchestrate the creation of a new user-requested game application flow session targeting the game server. The mapping of values is illustrated in Fig. 2. First, using our developed Game Client application, the user specifies the target Game Server IP address (Fig. 2, left) together with his/her own Game Client IP address as well as the Game ID that he/she wants to play. Then, by pressing the "Play" button, the user issues a QoD request to our CAMARA application (Fig. 2, right) to create the Application Flow session. After this step, our CAMARA implementation sends a request to create (or reuse) a Network Slice (modeled through the IETF Network Slice Model [10]) to support the user's application flow. This request first goes to the E2E MD (ETSI OSM), which in turn translates the IETF Network Slice Model into an IETF L3 Service Model (L3SM, based on RFC8299)[11], and sends it to the F5G Network MD (ETSI TFS) in order to establish an L3VPN service between the User Equipment and the Game Server VM. This L3VPN connectivity service is then deployed on the underlying testbed (described in the next section).

B. Testbed Description

The demonstration employed a testbed illustrating the architecture's capability to support QoD applications like cloud-based VR gaming. This included an intricate setup of the F5G-A infrastructure composed of Optical Network Terminal (ONT) equipment, Optical Line Terminal (OLT), Optical Transport Network (OTN), Edge Provider Equipment (PE), OTN Switches

Fig. 2: Creating a Gaming Application Flow Session

and Aggregation Edge equipment, culminating in access to VM gaming servers through an OpenStack cloud resource manager, shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Our Testbed and Lab Equipment

IV. DEMONSTRATION SHOWCASING

The attending users will have the opportunity to see a live demonstration of the proposed solution. There, the presenting author will carry a laptop with a VPN connection to the testbed and showcase (a) the deployment of the gaming service, and (b) the request of the gaming application flow. Due to logistics and technological limitations, the real VR gaming application will not be showcased; instead, a mocked game enabling the user to request the application flow will be used.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, a first-in-kind open-source and standards-based architecture for a NaaS platform is proposed and demonstrated. This platform is illustrated by a cloud-based VR Gaming use-case. This PoC not only highlighted a technological milestone but also set the stage for the future soft end-to-end quality-enabled telecommunications. By leveraging the latest ETSI standards and technologies, this collaboration exemplifies how the F5G-A architecture can support not just immersive and realistic VR gaming services but also a wide array of other highly-demanding digital services and applications.

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